

Analyzing and Adding Accident Prone Area's in Kerala into Google Map

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Abstract— One of the popular and most used Direction and web Mapping tool which is customer friendly is Google Maps. It maps the routes and directions into map and serves as an online/offline mapping tool. Google develop and maintains the Google map technology. Some of the features which it provides are Street view, Satellite imagery, direction, roads, speed, real-time traffic, re-routes to shorter routes, driving, flying (in beta), and taking public transportation are all accessible.

In this the accident prone areas are analyzed, studied. We get the accident prone are from the official website of Kerala Road Safety Authority (KRSA) The data is then visualized onto the custom map using Google My Maps. The Mapping is done based on the latitude and longitude information obtained from the data. There is Starting point and ending point on the plotted map which indicates the accident prone areas. The Location marker gives info about the number of accidents occurred in the place, number of causalities and many more information regarding the place

From the plotted map when a route is set between two places we can see the blackspot areas in the map. Providing an early information will help to reduce the number of accidents to a good extend.

I. INTRODUCTION

Google map was developed as a desktop program. Lars Rasmussen and Jens Rasmussen were the key developers of Google Maps. It was written in C++ language. Later in October 2004, google acquired their company, and then it was converted into a web application. Google also acquired Geospatial data visualization company and a traffic analyzer company which analyzed the real time traffic. With the combination of acquires company's technology Google Map was launched in February 2005 as a web application for its users.

The web application front end used the regular JavaScript, XML and Ajax. Google also offered embedding of map on third party websites for their business purpose use.

Keywords: Google Maps, Accident Prone Areas, Black spot, Latitude, Longitude

A. Features and other information of Google Map Platform

- Provide Map SDK for Android and iOS
- Maps API (JavaScript, Embed, Elevation)
- Show Shortest route using Direction, Road, Distance Matrix API
- Get users current location using Geolocation and Geocoding

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- Offers live location tracking
- Satellite imaging
- Street View

II. REQUIRMENTS

A. Any browser which support Google Map Web application

One of the best option to choose is Google Chrome with its latest version.

B. A Google Account

Once a Google account is created, all the features of Google can be Accesses using this account.

C. Google Drive

To store the Google Custom Map and the dataset required for the map.

D. Google Spreadsheets or MS Excel

A tabular arrangement to Store all the Location and all other related details.

E. Geocode by Awesome Table

It is a tool used in Google Spreadsheet to get the latitude and longitude information from the corresponding address entered by the user.

III. CREATING CUSTOM MAP IN GOOGLE MAP

Google map provides many features on of them is allowing to create a custom map. To make a custom map, you don't need any extra software or technology. You only need Google Maps to create your own custom map, which allows you to add your own pinpoints, shapes, and directions.

Steps involved are:

- Open Google map (<https://www.google.com/maps/>) and select the menu bar on the top left corner. OR Visit <https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/?hl=en>
- Navigate to *Your Places >> Maps >> Create Map*

(Fig: 3.0)

- After Clicking Create Map a new map is created, give a suitable name to the map and also provide some Description

(Fig: 3.1)

A. ADDING LAYERS TO THE MAP

We can add any number of layers to the map, the data which is location marker can be imported into the map. It Supports many formats

(Fig: 3.2)

IV. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The Kerala Road Safety Authority, which is supported by a dedicated Road Safety Fund, is working to improve road safety in the state by assisting stakeholder departments and District Road Safety Councils (DRSC). Via multi-sectoral road safety measures that explicitly target high-risk areas and vulnerable road users, the Authority hopes to reduce the risk of fatalities and serious injuries from road accidents. The Authority serves as the state's nodal agency for coordinating and implementing road safety programs. KRSA will work with the help of

stakeholders to make Kerala's roads clean safe for all modes of traffic.

By using the data obtained from the Kerala Road Safety Authority (KRSA) we can plot the accident prone area in Google map API

http://roadsafety.kerala.gov.in/assets/downloads/others/B_lackspot_list_2018.xlsx

V. IMPLIMENTATION

We need to create a google account for the implementation of the above data on to a map
Open the Blackspot list obtained from the KRSA website.
Which contain:

- Name of District
- Name of Police Station
- Location of Accident Spot
- Name and type of Road
- Landmarks
- Total number of accidents
- Latitude and Longitude information

Choose the necessary fields and copy the data into a Google spreadsheet and save it in the Google Drive

Sl. No.	Name of District	Name of Police Station	Location of Accident Spot	Name of Road	Total accidents	Total Fatalities	STARTING POINT (LAT, LONG)
1	Thiruvananthapuram	Accingal	Kozhik	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	48	19	8.670223, 76.835330
2	Thiruvananthapuram	City Traffic Police Station	Pattom to Plamoodu	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	238	14	8.518554, 76.842560
3	Thiruvananthapuram	City Traffic Police Station	Ananthapatt to Chakkal	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	197	13	8.489712, 76.821462
4	Thiruvananthapuram	City Traffic Police Station	Ovenkaryam to Pongasala	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	160	12	8.464796, 76.817229
5	Thiruvananthapuram	City Traffic Police Station	East Fort to Attalulangara	MC Road (C-02)	123	15	8.475988, 76.847470
6	Thiruvananthapuram	Heduvangad	Muthichery Jn.	Other Road	39	4	8.60273371, 77.002752
7	Thiruvananthapuram	Heyattikkara	Paluvayyala	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	58	20	8.410275, 77.074245
8	Thiruvananthapuram	Heyattikkara	Ankulmoor	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	48	20	8.414207, 77.081056
9	Thiruvananthapuram	Heyattikkara	Anaravida Toll Jn	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	42	13	8.388388, 77.099798
10	Thiruvananthapuram	Palode	Peringimala	Other Road	15	2	8.728631, 77.048532
11	Kollam	Chathannur	Chathannur Jn.	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	48	27	8.803975, 76.169882
12	Kollam	Chathannur	Speenatty Jn. to Karankodu	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	29	10	8.850271, 76.720919
13	Kollam	Chavara	Heendalara	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	43	20	8.938467, 76.544190
14	Kollam	Chavara	Chavara Jn.	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	34	15	8.972860, 76.534474
15	Kollam	Chavara	Sanganamangalam to Thirunam	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	26	9	8.944242, 76.523914
16	Kollam	Chavara	Muttittom	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	29	9	9.020885, 76.542063
17	Kollam	Chavara	Perinaman	Parivet - Kanyakumari Road	23	28	8.962781, 76.534620

(Fig: 5.0)

Create a custom map and add import the Spreadsheet into the Map.

(Fig: 5.1)

After successful import, we need to choose the column to

position the marker.

(Fig: 5.2)

And then choose the title of the marker.

The layer added will be reflected in the map.

We need to add two layers one for the starting point and other for the Ending point of the road, in between which the Accident prone area lies

(Fig: 6.1)

Sl. No.	L	M
1	STARTING POINT (LAT, LONG)	ENDING POINT (LAT, LONG)
2	8.670323, 76.835330	8.664764, 76.838972
3	8.518554, 76.942560	8.514050, 76.946074
4	8.486712, 76.927492	8.488943, 76.925489
5	8.548794, 76.917229	8.550935, 76.911028
6	8.479386, 76.947470	8.479413, 76.941472
7	8.60273371, 77.002752	8.60786, 77.002736
8	8.410275, 77.070435	8.41101, 77.06832

(Fig: 5.3)

On clicking the marker, we can see the details of the location.

VI. RESULT

Now we can see the location markers on the custom map that we created.

[View Map](#)

(Fig: 6.2)

VII. DESCRIPTION

After Successfully adding the Blackspots in the map. Consider travelling from A to B. There are many accident prone areas in between these two place, the traveler may or may not these places So he can set a direction from A to B in the custom map created and ride safely.

For example,

Consider a person is travelling from Kozhikode to Kottayam,

and he sets a direction in between these two places:

(Fig: 7.0)

Starting point:

(Fig: 7.1)

Ending Point:

(Fig: 7.2)

After Setting the direction we can see a route appeared in the map, we can also see the black spots where accidents take place. So the person can easily identify these areas and drive carefully through these areas.

(Fig: 7.3)

VIII. CONCLUSION

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Google Maps is one of the largest, free online map services in the world. With the help of Custom Maps, we can create our own map for many purposes. There are many other datasets which we can implement in the maps which can be helpful for many others while travelling or for finding some other locations. With the custom map we created above one can get an exact information about the accident prone areas while they are travelling from one place to another. With this we can prevent the accident rates.

We can also set Direction API, one can set route between two places and can exactly find the places which are the blackspots. This can prevent the rate of accidents while travelling to an unknown place.

Google map also provide many other API's and features which can be made useful. We can update a location marker with photos and videos of the place. Even Street View can also help to get an exact idea if the respective streets. Live Traffic monitoring helps to save our time and map automatically redirects to other roads with less traffic.

By Using all the free features provide by google map let's make our journey safe and also help others in their journey.

IX. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zheng et al., "Traffic Accident's Severity Prediction: A Deep-Learning Approach-Based CNN Network", IEEE Access, vol. 7, (2019)pp. 39897-39910.
- [2] Jun Liu, Alexander Hainen, Xiaobing Li, Qifan Nie, Shashi Nambisan., "Pedestrian injury severity in motor vehicle crashes: An integrated spatio-temporal modeling approach", Accident Analysis & Prevention(2019)
- [3] Juby Mathew, R Vijayakumar, "Multilinear Principal Component Analysis with SVM for Disease Diagnosis on Big Data", IETE Journal of Research, 1-15, (2019) Taylor & Francis.
- [4] Liyamol Isen et al., "Identification And Analysis Of Accident Black Spots Using GIS", International Journal of Innovative Research in Science Engineering and Technology An ISO 3297: 2007 Certified Organization, vol. 2, no. 1, 2013.
- [5] Heejin Jeong, Youngchan Jang, Patrick J. Bowman, Neda Masoud, "Classification of motor vehicle crash injury severity: A hybrid approach for imbalanced data", Accident Analysis & Prevention, vol.120, (2018)pp.250-261